

Microwave enhanced synthesis of oximes from ketones

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Microwave enhanced synthesis of oximes from ketones in high yields is reported.

Oximes, derivative of carbonyls, are of great interest for protection of carbonyls, as they are readily prepared and highly stable compounds¹. Oximes are extensively used for purification and characterisation of carbonyls and in the conversion of amides via Beckmann rearrangement². Synthesis of oximes from noncarbonyl compounds³ provides an alternative route to aldehydes and ketones. Besides the Beckmann rearrangement, oximes can be conveniently converted into nitrile⁴, nitrocompounds⁵, gemhalonitrocom-

pounds⁶, isoxazolines⁷, vinyl isonitriles⁸, nitrones⁹, primary¹⁰ or secondary¹¹ amines and stabilised carbanions¹².

Recently the wide applicability of microwave irradiation in chemical reaction enhancement^{13,14} is due to high reaction rates and formation of cleaner products. Herein we wish to report the microwave enhanced synthesis of oximes from ketones within a few minutes in high yields (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary on an electrically heated metal block and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (BPL, BMO-700 T, 1200 W).

General procedure: A solution of a ketone (5.0 mmol) in alcohol (2.0 ml), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g) and sodium acetate (2.0 g) in water (10.0 ml) was taken in a 100-ml Erlenmeyer flask fitted with a funnel as a loose top upon which a round-bottomed flask containing ice was placed to serve as a condenser. The reaction mixture was then irradiated under microwave for few minutes. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol. The products were characterised by comparing the m.ps. and ir spectra of the authentic samples.

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Table 1. Results of microwave enhanced synthesis of oximes

Sl. no.	Substrate	Product	Time min	Yield %	M.p./B.p. °C
1		10	92	58	
2		10	93	91	
3		10	98	59	
4		8	94	88	
5		8	93	87	
6		3	97	117	
7		1	98	174	
8		1	96	145	
9		7	98	151	
10		7	96	149	
11		10	92	155	
12		10	97	237	

Note

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